

The Emerging Development in Nigeria's Construction Industry: The Place of a Quantity surveyor

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ABSTRACT

The size of the Nigerian construction industry relatively small as compared to other sectors of the economy. In 2008, the industry made up to 0.2% of the value of the global construction industry which was about \$3.15bn. It also out grown some other sectors with an impressive percentage of 12.1% despite the fact that its growth is directly and indirectly linked to the government expenditure on infrastructure in 2005. The quantity surveyors as a chartered professionals are not left out in this trends of emerging development. The profession has evolved from been a craft to a well-respected profession today. The contribution and services offered by quantity surveyors in the construction processes are increasing rapidly in scope and size. The expectations chain of quantity surveyors have also increased in length as a result of introduction of modern technologies, complicated client, and emergence of new rules and regulations. Therefore, in order to remain active and maintain a competitive edge among other professionals, quantity surveyors need to diversify their contributions and services towards the success of any construction activities in the industry. Today, quantity surveying profession is now encroaching into various fields and roles such as Implementation of ICT to solve practical problems, Investment appraisal, Risk analysis, Value management, Environmental services, Sub-contract administration, Valuation for insurance purpose, Technical Auditing, Insolvency services, Project Management, Administering Maintenance programmes, Advice on contractual dispute, Parametric estimating, Planning and Supervision, etc. This article examines the emerging development in the construction industry and the place of a quantity surveyor in Nigeria's construction industry.

1.0 Overview of Nigeria's Construction Industry

The Nigeria construction industry has undergone various forms of restructuring from the age of simple buildings to the age of high rise buildings including implementation of modern technologies into the construction industry such as computer aided design (CAD), building information modelling (BIM), automated IT packages, E-tendering, etc. These ICT has brought about increase in the productivity of this sector which made it outgrow other sectors of the economy. The growth of the Nigeria's construction industry can be projected to the increase in government infrastructural investment which booms the sector (Dantata Sanusi, 2008). The industry is known to be the largest employer of with an estimated number of over millions employees. Through the provision of job opportunities, the industry is a vital contributor to the growth of the country (Confederation of International Constructor's Association (CICA), 2002).

In a developing country like Nigeria, construction industry of comprises of the specialist contractor, building and civil engineering industry which has been a major contributor to the economic growth of Nigeria through the provision of roads, bridges, residential accommodation, social services and utilities, industrial and recreational facilities. In early 1940, Nigeria's real time construction contracting began with very few foreign companies operating (Olowo-Okere, 1985).

After Independence in 1960, the construction industry was catalyzed by the oil boom in the 1970s which brought an improvement in construction activities and lasted up to 1983. An overwhelming upsurge has been witnessed in Nigeria's construction industry due to the fact that most construction contracting are dominated by non-indigenous companies with few indigenous companies (Idoro, 2009). Unfortunately, Nigeria's low level of human resources development required for; constructing, designing, maintaining and planning of projects was exposed during this period of time. However, with establishment of improved training institutions, engagement of foreigners in construction project, political stability, collaborations between indigenous and foreign entrepreneurs, and improved government policies to enhance relationship between countries, the apparent resources gap needed for successful completion of complex projects between indigenous companies and their foreign counterparts are now closer compared to the pre-independence era (Mbamali and Okotie, 2012).

1.1 Overview of Quantity Surveying Profession

Quantity surveying profession exists to ensure the judicious allocation of the construction resources of materials, manpower, machinery, money, methods and management with the overriding aim of ensuring value for money spent on construction projects. Alternatively, Quantity surveyor is a professional in the construction industry that deals with cost related issues.

Traditionally, the services that a competent quantity surveyors provide include estimating quantities and cost, cost planning and management, feasibility and viability studies for building works to be executed so as to advice the client on the best alternative, compilation and documentation of contractual issues which may arise in the process of execution, and tendering. The modern quantity surveyors perform various types of services to the client or contractor depending on the party the quantity surveyor belongs to, the one for the client is called the consultant quantity surveyor which assist the client in efficient utilization of resources available while the contractor quantity surveyor helps the client to maximize profit.

The quantity surveyor is the expert who is concerned with financial integrity, contractual matters, procurement, and delivering value for the clients' money invested. The services that the quantity surveyors currently provide have shifted from the 'downstream' to 'upstream'. Quantity surveying profession assumes an important and irreplaceable position in the construction industry. They are required to provide clients with preliminary advice on the cost implication the client is about to embark on. The profession render services associated with procurement, value and cost of projects which in turn help the client achieve value for money and utilize the available resources effectively from inception to completion, contract administration and project management. Due to the diversification and changing in expectation quantity surveying profession, the need to produce hybrid and competent graduate to tackle this challenges arises (Zakaria, Che Munaaim, and Khan, 2006).

The dynamism of quantity surveying has also enable the profession to venture into other areas like value management, facility management, project management, risk management, centre management, maintenance management, arbitration, system management, and knowledge management. In fact, quantity surveyors are adaptable creatures capable of reinventing themselves according to the demands of the modern progressive clients (Cartlidge, 2003).

1.2 New ICT Revolution in the Construction Industry

In the technology age today, professionals from different part of the world can unite together to work on a construction project. Two principal phenomena, free market economy and rapid advancement in information and communication technology (ICT) are practically working for the rapid transformation of the whole world into a global village where goods and services can be made available with minimum restrictions and delays. The project team for a building may therefore involve professionals from widely distributed geographical areas, sometimes on different continents (Madigan 1993).

Contract documents can be transferred through E-mails. Briefs can be transferred to the architect through electronic email, and the architect thereby prepares the drawings, then send the drawing to the structural engineer to prepare the structural drawing and specifications, the architectural and structural drawings, and specifications is then sent to the quantity surveyor to prepare the contract documents which one of the main component is the Bill of Quantities. As an estimator construction quantities and cost, quantity surveyors have been greatly influenced by the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) revolution. In the construction industry today, there are several development of IT packages designed to execute specific tasks such as measurement and quantification of construction quantities, abstracting and preparation of Bill of Quantities which has fundamentally change working practices and patterns in the industry. In recent years, architects have made increasing use of computer aided design (CAD) in the form of 2D drafting and 3D modelling for the production of project information. The quantity surveyor can then estimate the quantities manually or use the available measurement and quantification IT packages using the 2D drafting or 3D modelling which may require little manual effort depending on the complexity of the work. It also improves procurement process through the definition of items and work sections that facilitate sourcing for labour and materials for construction contracts, to synchronise with the Classification of Construction Cost Information and the Classification of Construction Resources Information. Many quantity surveyors cannot afford to install most of this IT packages because of purchase high cost, this has now diversified quantity surveying profession into programming. Quantity surveyors that have vast knowledge of Information and Communication Technology can now customize softwares by formulating algorithm using any of the available programming languages that the quantity surveyor is skilled at, this in turn speed up taking-off, abstracting and bill preparation process. A typical example of a customize measurement software is CBQUES;

The screenshot displays the CBQUES software interface. The window title is "Computerized Building Quantity Estimation System (CBQUES) - [Automated Take-Off 1]". The menu bar includes "CBQUES", "View", "Tools", "Windows", "Girth Estimator", "Mensuration", and "Help". The main area is divided into "INPUT" and "OUTPUT" sections. The "INPUT" section is further divided into "EXTERNAL" and "INTERNAL" columns, with a sub-tab "Estimate Girth". Each column contains various input fields for dimensions and rates, and a "Description" box. The "OUTPUT" section also has "EXTERNAL" and "INTERNAL" columns, showing calculated values for volumes and amounts. At the bottom, there are "Compute" and "Clear" buttons for each input section.

Computerized Building Quantity Estimation System (CBQUES) - [Automated Take-Off 1]

CBQUES View Tools Windows Girth Estimator Mensuration Help

Concrete Column Base and Starter Foundation Blockwork Fillings DPM and DPC Mesh Reinforcement Over-Site Concrete Preliminaries Bill Measured Works Bill Material Schedule

S/N	DESCRIPTION	QTY	UNIT	RATE	AMOUNT
	SUBSTRUCTURE (Provisional)				
	GROUNDWORK				
	D20: EXCAVATION AND FILLING				
	SITE PREPARATION				
A	Clear site of all shrub, bushes, undergrowth, trees not exceeding 600mm girth, large stones rubbish, debris etc and remove from site.		m2		
	EXCAVATION				
B	Excavate topsoil for preservation, average depth of 150mm commencing from the natural ground level.		m2		
C	Excavate foundation trenches starting from stripped level width exceeding 300mm and max depth not exceeding 1.0 m		m3		
D	Excavate foundation trenches starting from stripped level width not exceeding 300mm and max depth not exceeding 1.0 m		m3		
E	Level and compact bottom of excavation to receive concrete, width 675mm		m2		
F	Level and compact bottom of excavation to receive concrete, width 450mm		m2		

The dimensions are inserted manually into the program and the program automatically estimate building quantities and prepare bill of quantities.

1.3 Value Management

The construction industry is expanding and growing rapidly, in other to meet up with this trends, quantity surveyors need to have a good knowledge of value management. Value can simply be defined as the level of importance that is placed on a particular item. Value management on the other hand is a term widely used in the United Kingdom (UK) to describe the overall structured, team-based approach to a construction project. It helps in addressing the value process during the conception, definition, implementation and operation phases of a construction project. It involves a set of logical and systematic procedures and techniques to enhance project value throughout the life span of that facility (Lewis, 2008).

New building materials are being introduced into the industry as a result of advancement in technology so as to make the environment friendly and hazard free for the people which in turn leads to the extinction of the old building materials. For quantity surveying profession to survive with the emerging development in the construction industry today, such quantity surveyor must be vast in new construction technology available in the 21st century so as to apply various value management principles which enhance value.

1.4 Technical Auditing

Technical auditing is also a new development in the construction industry that can be used to fight corruption. Technical auditing involves the examination of the technical aspect of a construction project. This is better examined by professionals concerned with such technicalities. Generally, technical auditing is mostly used to verify the cost of construction projects where drawings and specification only were the basis of the contract and variations have also been involved. Several years ago, accusations had been piled on the high cost and malpractice in the public works administration, (Mogbo, 1998). Many expensive engineering projects have been designed, supervised and final accounts settled by officers in charge that are representing the interest of the client which maybe private individuals or government without post or on-going work audit, (Mogbo, 1999).

1.5 Risk Management

The Nigeria's construction industry is subjected to varieties of risks and uncertainty than other industries. Traditionally, quantity surveyors present a single price estimate to the client, although on virtually every project differences would occur between this single sum and the final account sum. Since risk can be measured, it can be accounted for in the estimate. Due to the importance of accounting for risk in an estimate, the quantity surveyor in cost forecasting of the new project will assess different sorts of cost data and coupled with his expertise will produce a budget price range calculated within a confidence limits.

Quantity surveyors need to be skilled at identifying, analyzing and quantifying risk because as the construction industry is advancing, the complexity of construction project is also increasing together with uncertainties. As the complexity of the structures increases, the assumptions and errors also increases which may render the estimate unacceptable. In view of this, the parametric method of estimate is being introduced so as to meet this challenges and reduce the errors in preparation of estimate. Several methods have been used for uncertainty and risk analysis when estimating construction costs (Paek et al, 1993). The likely risk attached to the project is been estimated using statistical parameters.

The backbone of parametric estimating is the probability and estimation theory. Parameter can be define as a population characteristics. A parameter is an important element to consider in the evaluation or comprehension of an event, project or situation. Consider a system modeled by a linear algebraic equation; or differential equation; or partial differential equation, which involves dependent and independent variables; and also certain constants. The constants may be parameters. The main aim of using this method is to obtain the reliable and optimal estimate of these parameters using the measured values of input and output variables.

Risk analysis is also important when advising a client or an organization on the project to be undertaken. The quantity surveyor must critically examine the factors that can affect such project, factors of which can be; cost of finance, profitability ratio, business climatic condition, non-economic consideration.

1.6 Facility Management

The aspect of facility management is another emerging development in the Nigeria construction industry. Facility management is a very broad area which quantity surveyors are gradually encroaching into. Facility management is the process of controlling and ensuring the effective use of a building during the useful life of the building. It involves various areas such as maintenance, post occupancy evaluation, etc. (en.wikipedia.com). As more sophisticated buildings are emerging, the need for building maintenance increases. This become a fertile field for quantity surveyors with vast knowledge of building materials and maintenance technology. Building maintenance is simply described in BS 3811 (1964) as work done to keep or restore a building to its initial state and thus prevent further destruction of the property. The already constructed buildings needs to be maintained so as to increase the value and also increase the useful life of the building.

1.7 Electronic tendering

Electronic tendering is another emerging development in the industry. The exchange of contract document by digital files and electronic communications has been normal practice within the construction sector for some time, indeed tender documentation has often been supported by the use of floppy disks, CD-ROMs or even, in some cases, e-Mails. However e-Tendering is more fundamental because it involves the digitalization of tendering process. It is the conduct of the complete tendering exercise from the advertising of the requirement through to the placing of the contract, including the exchange of all relevant documentation all by electronic communication (*en.wikipedia.com*). Ultimately, contract management and the monitoring of contract performance will be conducted by electronic communications. It has helped to enhance tendering and procurement process which tenderers can submit their tenders through electronic media, it is then evaluated by the criterion set by the quantity surveyor alongside with members of the evaluation committee who are to consider the tender that is economical and within the stipulated budget of the committee which is then incorporated into the design of the electronic tendering process and the system automatically performs the selection operation which reduce the rate of favouritism in the process of awarding a construction project and hence reduce corruption significantly because only little human effort is not used in the selection of the best contractor. Favouritism has led to the abandonment of many construction project in which the contract fall into the hand of the incompetent contractor that lack the necessary expertise that is required in the project. This process of tendering is not often used in Nigeria because there is no provision for it in the current procurement Act of 2007. E-tendering provide for varieties of advantage such as fast and better information, increased security and integrity of tendering and automation of the evaluation process (*UNESCO, 2009*)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

As a result of the afore-said, quantity surveying profession is becoming more diversified as a result of rapid advancement in the construction industry. For the future of quantity surveyors to be secured, adequate training need to be offered to prospective graduate so as to fit into the industry and carry out their function effectively. Ever since the shift in power from the military regime to the current civilian, The Nigeria's construction industry has undergone tremendous increase which has helped to reform the economy of the country especially the construction industry. The quantity surveyors are not left out in this development trends and therefore need to be vaster in many areas so as to adapt and fit in to the current state of the construction industry.

Recommendations

This article thereby recommends that:

1. An individual practicing quantity surveying must have studied Quantity surveying and project management underpinned with gained experience through practical exposure. This will assist such individual to carry out planning, scheduling, control and coordination effectively.
2. Incorporation of engineering courses and courses relating to economics, statistics, financial management or analysis and risks management among others into the curriculum of tertiary institutions offering quantity surveying programme. This will enable the resultant Quantity Surveyors to be the most desired specialists in the Cost management and analysis practice.
3. Quantity surveyors should be ICT oriented. This will assist Quantity surveyors in so many ways such as speed in bill preparation, speed in cost analysis, documentation, etc.
4. Practicing quantity surveyors must have knowledge of law. This will enable them to know the legal implication of the activities undertaken.
5. Incorporation of E-tendering process into the procurement Act.

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